

Historiographic Metafiction Technique: A Postmodern Study of Toni Morrison's Song of Solomon

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 17, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Song of Solomon, historiography, metafiction approach, Toni Morrison, postmodernism.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4488259</p>	<p><i>Throughout employing the historiographicmetafiction technique, the current manuscript presents a close reading and investigating of Toni Morrison's Song of Solomon and to depict the significance of the past and its literary explanation. The manuscript's main goal is to study the historical novel in the postmodern age that is categorized as historiographicmetafiction, a term which refers to the mingling of history and fiction, and permits for various alternative voices and additional histories by destroying the proceedings and historical records which they indicate to. This paper will also present an overview of postmodernism as the theoretical basis of Toni Morrison's Song of Solomon which is going to be explored as a model of historiographicmetafiction novel.</i></p>

1. Introduction

1.2 Historiography and Metafiction: Overview

Postmodernism is defined as a deferent phenomenon which represents a reaction against the previous ages at the end of the Second World War. Several writers and thinkers have been influenced by this new philosophy, among them the Afro-American novelists. Therefore, they tend to employ the narrative technique of historiography and metafiction in their postmodern novel to demonstrate that history is continually misleading us to the reality of events. They work in accordance with postmodernism theory. Those writers have seized this philosophy to form the black postmodernist genre which deals with the black life to present their concerns throughout counting upon diverse methods and techniques. One of those novelists is Toni Morrison whose fictions serve to offer the suffering and the history of her Afro-American people through the use of a new method of narration, which is known as historiographical metafiction.

In spite of the fact that metafiction is invented in the year 1970s by William Gass, an American critic, metafiction has gained its best definition by Patricia Waugh who has described metafiction as a term that is "given to fictional writing which self-consciously and systematically draws attention to its status as an artefact in order to pose questions about the relationship between fiction and reality" (Waugh, 1984:2). It is used to lay the emphasis on the structure of a novel to attract the attention of the readers to the works of fiction. In the use of different metafictional methods, the writing will not only survey the essential arrangements of narrative in fiction, but they also discover the probable fictionality of the external world of "the literary fictional writing" (Ibid).

An emphasizes is directed towards the recent metafiction's self-critical inclination by portraying it as the borderline speech, a sort of composing which dwells itself on the frontier between criticism and fiction, and which accepts the border to be its issues (Currie, 1995:2). Moreover, some critics involve works which are slightly metafictional by considering the sensationalized novelist or narrator as metanarrative strategies to interpret a significant attribution of fiction as metafiction (Currie, 1995:2). Waugh characterizes the obvious utilization of metafictional procedure, as branches from modernist examining of reality and consciousness. The ensuing terms are recycled to label contemporary metafiction as auto-representational, self-conscious, introverted, introspective or narcissistic technique (Currie, 1995:14).

Many theorists have approved that metafiction is difficult to be categorized as a genre or by the absolute means of postmodern fiction. They propose that metafiction shows a self-reflexivity induced by the novelist's knowledge of the theory implying the structure of fictional texts, deprived of separating current metafiction from ancient works comprising like self-reflective procedures (Waugh, 1984:2). According to Hutcheon, "the meeting of metafiction and historiography produces a new kind of experimental writing uniquely capable of fulfilling the poetics of postmodernism" (Hutcheon, 1995:71)

The experimental writings like the experimental novel which is presented as one who fractures the pacts of its time. It shows that what is found in experimental at one occasion perhaps is regarded as a normal at another. Nowadays, experimental novels in literature are categorized as metafiction; it is also seen as a kind of narrative that has challenged the tradition by destroying the impression of fiction (experimental-novel). Hutcheon states that historiographicmetafiction is connected with postmodern literature especially with novel. The works that are related to this term are famous and public novel that are powerfully self-reflexive. The self-conscious fiction is presented in the aim of discovering the relation between the random linguistic structure and the whole world to what it aims to refer or to denote to the relation between the world outside the fiction with that which is inside the fiction (Waugh,1984:3).

In *a Poetics of Postmodernism*, Hutcheon grades the historical novel in postmodernism as historiographicmetafiction for the reason that these historical novels thematise the theory of present historiography and problematize the difference between fiction and history. This definition pressured on the historical novel and strengths self-consciousness around the manner according to what these stress are done (Hutcheon,1991:113). Hutcheon's definition directed by the paradox formed by the combination of historical reality and metafictional self-reflexivity in the novels that are powerfully paradoxically and self-reflexive to place the pretension to historical actions and figures.

Modernist and postmodernist writers have investigated the challenges of the specialist of the histories by admitting that the point offered is the writer's subjective clarification. Historiographicmetafictions are novels which are strongly self-reflective, but they reestablish the genetically perspective "into metafiction and problematize" the whole demand of historical knowing (Hutcheon,1987:285-286). As a result of that historiographicmetafiction has filled the crack among the historical and the fictional writings by reemerging both of these two genres. They appoint "a questioning stance through their common use of conventions of narrative, of reference, of the inscribing of subjectivity, of their identity as textuality, and even of their implication in ideology" (Ibid :286).

Beyond the re-joining of fiction and history, Hutcheon comments that postmodern fiction inspires her to edit or to exemplify the historical events in fiction and in history in which both situations are to prohibit it from existing as crucial, teleological and to re-open it up in the present, ("Hutcheon,1987:209). In the aim of achieving this re-performance of the bygone, historiographicmetafiction, "plays upon the truth and lies of the historical record. Certain known historical details are deliberately falsified in order to foreground the possible mnemonic failures of recorded history and the constant potential for both deliberate and inadvertent error" (Hutcheon,1987:294). In addition, historiographicmetafiction is depicted as the re-introducing of history to a postmodern fiction by the contemporary writers or poets who are using the various terms in literature to show the old-fashioned means of re-depiction of history. (Malpas,2005:101)

In this technique postmodernism can catch the lies and the rights that are taken from both fiction and history. It reflects the conditions of history that are always discussed and structured in the inclusion of ideology. Hence, Linda Hutcheon tends to use the term of historiographicmetafiction to deal with the compilation of fiction to collect the literary devices of historical fiction and metafiction (Hutcheon,1988:120). It is argued that historiographicmetafiction blends theory, history and fiction. Therefore, the reflection of history and its subject as well as the historical events are clearly shown in historiography. The three genres of history, theory and literature are included by gathering the metafictional elements with history as one component. The division of the historical and the literary is defied by postmodern theory. Both of the inter-textual writing and linguistic constructs are devoted to reconsidering and revising of the shapes and the objects of the past (Hutcheon 1988:5). This term is clear in the year 1980s. It is not in the second area related to historical novel as many writers say such as Monika Fludrinski who depicts it as a text of the novel in the 20th century. (Marc,2003:45)

The term historiographicmetafiction is not involved by the investigation of the actual value of the past impersonation, but with the matter of the one who is able to control on history. Accordingly, in historiographicmetafiction, the concepts of historical "truths" are built theoretically to be asserted. The calamities of the bygone are likely historical 'facts', but the only events that are selected to be told are turned to be facts. The variance between wanton proceedings and the gifted facts is regarded as one to which postmodern novel sounds maniac. (Hutcheon ,1991:75)

The events of the past and historical figures that are excluded by history so as not to be involved in it, become one of the main attempts that historiographicmetafiction tries to concentrate on. Historiographicmetafiction seeks to make these events to be forefront and to retell the stories of the past. Hutcheon asserts this concept when she mentions that historiographicmetafiction "mean those well-known and popular novels which are both intensely self-reflexive and yet paradoxically also lay claim to historical events and personages". (Hutcheon,1988:5)

Hutcheon argued that historiographicmetafiction is employed in the postmodern novels to show the history and its conditions which can be alternately structured and discussed around the implication of ideology. Historiographicmetafiction advocates the bounds of "event" and "fact" which jointed by utmost of historian, with the aim to gaze occasions which can be truthful. It hence utilizes the pact of Para-textual bringing it from

history, particularly note to designate and combine the power and topicality from the foundation and clarification of the past (Hutcheon,1988:120). La Capra debates that the past reached for us in the shape of texts and textualized archives, records, monuments, remainders-memories, and published writings, and so on. As a result, these manuscripts interact with each other in a compound way (Capra 1985:128). It is of importance to portray the some of the main features historiographicmetafictionsuch as:

- 1- Historiographicmetafiction stains the range between history and fiction.
- 2- Historiographicmetafiction proposes that the continuing relation of (fact and fiction) like a dissent.
- 3- It has such features as parody, intertextuality and paratextuality.
- 4- The main factors that make historiographicmetafiction are character, time, the destruction of the plot, irony, dialogue, playfulness and paranoia.

Hutcheon adds that the historiographicmetafiction involves two terms that are historical fiction and postmodern fiction. Both of these terms are different as it is seen by many critics especially with that of the notion of truth and the affection of history in determining the role of the numerous expressions that exist according to those terms. Then, she sheds light on the difference between historical fiction and postmodern fiction through the following major features: First of all, the historical fiction centred on the historical idea that is implied in the story in such way of historical re-depicted by the writer to be the historical image that is different from the present. While postmodern fiction is centred on the character who is regarded as a whimsical or isolated person. The author in his novel characterizes the fact and the situation of his character to form his narrative. The second variance is that in historical fiction the central character of history has a moral incline, meanwhile, in postmodern fiction; the central character does not have a moral incline.

The third difference between historical novel and postmodern fiction is filled by presenting historical fiction's central character of history in a way of supporting the fictional story. Whereas, postmodern fiction calls for the ontological subjects and questions such as the question of how people know about the past and what they know at their present time. The last distinction between them is shown by mirroring the idea of postmodern fiction in which it utilizes two distinctive ways throughout the story .The first one by digging the historical truth in the aim purposefully of refuted the past records and the second by using past dates. On the other hand the historical fiction is built by the disability of the writer in utilizing true historical so that by writing the story the truth will not be relevant. However, as a result of that historical fiction uses both of the ways of postmodernism so as to introduce the meaning of specificity and trust in their writing (Hutcheon,1991:113-116). In the light of what is stated above, the present study endeavours to hypothesize the next points:

- 1-Historiographicmetafiction approach is viable to Toni Morrison's novel *Song of Solomon*.
- 2- *Song of Solomon* exemplifies the potentials of historical pastiche and self-reflexivity.
- 3-There is relationship between history and metafiction.

Then, the study will be conducted according to many leading questions that are mirrored as in the following:

- 1-What is *Historiographicmetafiction*?
- 2-Is *Historiographicmetafiction* used as tool in re-writing the history in the Afro-American *Song of Solomon*?
- 3- Can *Song of Solomon* serve in a way of retelling historical events such as slavery or others?
- 4- Does Morrison have a reason for re-writing history?
- 5- Does *Song of Solomon* mingle history and Fantasy?

1.3 Literature review

There are several studies and books that have been written and published about Toni Morrison's novels and writings. The first example is M. L. Roper's(1999) *Beating back the past: Toni Morrison's beloved as historiographicmetafiction* studies Morrison's *Beloved* as a metafiction novel. McLeod's "Re-writing History: Postmodern and postcolonial Negotiations in The fiction of J.G Farrell, Timonthy Mo, Kazuo Ishiguro and Salman Rushdie" in the year 1995, which focuses on finding the critics of the history of postmodernism and on the fiction of the contemporary history in English. There are many previous studies that have investigated the technique of historiographicmetafiction upon which this paper is built. An example is that of Kirca in his thesis under the topic "Postmodernist Historical Novel: Jeanette Winterson's and Salman Rushdie's Novel as a Historiographicmetafiction" in the year 2009. The aim of this thesis is to show how postmodern novel builds the history which does not care to the manuscript history. Patricia Waugh's (1984) *Metafiction the theory and practice of self-conscious fiction* presents the definition and theory of metafiction as self-conscious novel. One more example is displayed by the article of Noorbakhsh and Amjad's "Three Approaches Towards Historiographic: The French Lieutenant's, Possession and Waterland". Their aim is to examine and show the effect of history on the novels that are chosen by them. There are countless studies about the subject of metafiction and its employment in many fictional works. Yet there is no study written about the employing the metafiction approach in Morrison's *The Song of Solomon*. So this manuscript is considered the first study that explored this subject; this represents the novelty of the current manuscript. The sample of this study is Morrison's novel , *Song of Solomon*, which is the result of a real story, but it is still having the concerning of

fiction that needs investigating to find its historical events to be a representation of historical issues documented by the novelist. The historical representation of this notion perhaps is not the original context, but it is presentation of these historical ideas in the same situation.

2. The employment of historiographic metafiction in Tony Morrison's *The Song of Solomon*

Toni Morrison is one of the essential American postmodernist novelists whose well-known works outline the black features and expose the permeable mood of the American identity and practice. She is professed in the blacks' affairs and the case of slavery. She has started along with other writers to utilize the African myth so as to bring Africa to those who are taken from their continent to the American continent and likewise closer to their descendants. Throughout her own literary works, she attempts to regain the African people into their identity by the mediation of the past and by using the African methodology.

Predominantly, Morrison's *Song of Solomon* is regarded as a prominent sample adopting the postmodern approach "Historiographic Metafiction". Morrison's novel expounds her pledge to the life of black and culture as well as to discuss the part of African Americans in connection to the society of the white and the entail of slavery on the practice and the history of the black American people. The analysis of *Song of Solomon* is going to be carried out according to the following assumptions:

1- Morrison's Novel is a mingling of history and fantasy

2- It is a re-writing of the past.

3- Morrison has a reason for re-writing history.

4- There is a connection between fact and fiction.

This novel consists of fifteen chapters, in two parts; that introduces a story of searching for the history of the family which is about legends, myths and facts as well as dates. The protagonist is Milkman Dead who is in his way to find his identity and his past, which are regarded like a bond with Morrison as "Morrison's one's past determines one's identity" (Beaulieu 1985:21). The first part doesn't present slavery as a matter of fact, but it is the racism to be a matter of mindset. It shows how the Africans given new names when they arrived to the shores of America and how they become poor and being exploited even by the rich black people.

In the first part of this novel, Macon Dead asks his son Milkman to steal and regain the gold of their family from Pilate:

Let the things you own own other things. Then you'll own yourself and other people too", (Morrison, 1978:55). In another speech "get it and you can have half of it; go whatever you want. Get it. For both of us, please get it son. Get the gold. (Morrison 1978:173)

Here, Morrison presents the quest that will make the black discover the heritage of his family. This point embodies the starting point in re-writing the past to achieve the aim of historiographic metafiction. She depicts the reality of America especially with legacy of slavery or those whose names haven't any mention in any historical texts. The link is in milkman's quest in his search of ancestors. She used the buried stories of the past in a period of slavery to re-write history in the present. *Song of Solomon* is the story of searching for identity among the history of the dead's:

How many dead lives and fading memories were buried in and beneath the names of the places in the country? Under the recorded names where other names, just as "Macon Dead", recorded for all time in some dusty file, hide from view the real names of people, places and things. Names that had meaning". (Morrison, 1978:334)

The significance of the names is linked with the personality of the African Americans whose names are buried by time out of recording it in the history. Morrison utilizes this situation to retell it as historical events.

The second part of the novel illustrates how the quest of finding the heritage of the family leads Milkman to retell the history of the past in which his family had lived to restore that history in the present time. First of all, he discovers the approach of naming his ancestors, "White people name Negroes as race horses" (Ibid:245). In point of fact, he completes his quest and finds the appearing of his ancestor's names everywhere:

Everybody in the town is named Solomon, he thought wearily. Solomon's General Store, Luther Solomon (no relation), Solomon's Leap, and now the children were singing "Solomon don't leave me" instead of "Sugarman". Even the name of the town sounded like Solomon: Shalimar, which Mr. Solomon and everybody else pronounced Shallemon. (Ibid:305)

Then, Milkman knows how his grandfather escapes to Africa and left his story with his sons and children to save their story in their songs and games:

Solomon don't leave me here Cotton balls to choke me O Solomon don't leave me here Bukra's arms to yoke me. Solomon done fly, Solomon done gone Solomon cut across the sky, Solomon gone home. (Ibid:306-307)

This song retells the history of his family and solves all the puzzles as well as presenting pictures about the past time not to demonstrate it as only Milkman's quest, but to shed light on Morrison's own quest of finding the identity of the Afro-American people. And that's what is reflected in the next quote to show the discovery of his identity holding the history of his ancestors:

He almost shouted when he heard "Heddy took him to a red man's house." Heddy was Susan Byrd's grandmother on her father's side, and therefore Sing's mother too. And "red man's house" must be a reference to the Byrds as Indians. Of course! Sing was an Indian or part Indian and her name was Sing Byrd or more likely, Sing Bird, No- Singing Bird!... And her brother, Crowell Byrd, was probably Crow Bird or just Crow. They had mixed their Indian names with American sounding names. Milkman had four people now that he could recognize in the song: Solomon, Jake, Ryna and Heddy ... These children were singing a story about his own people! He hummed and chuckled as he did his best to put it all together. (Ibid:307)

By observing all these events, Milkman realizes his own identity by the songs that tell his own history and the past of his ancestors in the town of Shalimar and the story of their flying back to Africa so he feels pride by the heritage of his family. Milkman proves his knowing of his heritage by singing the songs as that of Pilates Dead's death).

These extracts grants the objective of the novelist to re-write the history of the past according to historiographicmetafiction approach, while the following extracts mirror the novel as path of mingling history and fantasy: "He could fly! You-hear me? My great-granddaddy could fly! He didn't need no airplane... He could fly to his own self" (Ibid:331-332). This extract epitomizes the myth of the history of his family and how they are able to fly in the air without airplane. As a matter of fact, this myth and legends make Milkman discover the rich heritage of his past and feels spirit liberated by the heritage of his family.

The end of the novel displays Milkman's symbolic leap into the past by his last leap. The reception of ancestor's flying myths allows him to improve his identity by legitimating other histories (Beaulieu,2003:21). The search for the history of his family takes him to catch his family rich heritage as an Afro-American. Ultimately, this novel exhibits that Milkman's quest starts as a quest for stealing the gold of his family from Pilate to the quest of finding the golden history of his family through which he was able to restore the lost names of his ancestors that are buried with the passing of history as well as for the symbolic meaning of the fly that symbolized the flying from slavery as a great symbol of the suffering of the Afro-American. With Milkman's discovery, the Afro-American bones can be buried with the past and offers the restoration of past events in the present as well as putting guidelines for the Afro-American life in the future.

Agreeing with Linda Hutcheon that the crucial features of such postmodern metafiction genre as *The Song of Solomon* are their emphasis on "the past of the formerly excluded ex-centric"; and she is content that not only history has a truth claim, but "both history and fiction are discourses and both derive their major truth claim from that identity". The utmost clear evaluation that "historiographicmetafiction" marks of the old-fashioned history are the festival of counter recall as an earnings to create the past. (Ropero,1999:174)

Morrison's novels always involve elements of the supernatural or magical so that several critics match her novels with the works of the "magical realists of Latin American". By depending on the model of historiographicmetafiction the mingling of history and fantasy is shown at the end of the novel according to which Milkman, the protagonist, has learned how to fly. After asking Morrison about the fantasy and the presence of supernatural in her novels, she states that she wants her works to arrest on the huge imagination of black society. Actually, Morrison's works mirrors the mixture of imaginative of the real world. (Carris& Michael,2005:51)

Finally, it is worthy to mention that the technique of Hutcheon's historiographical metafiction is applicable to Morrison's *The Song of Solomon* through which the relation between history and literature appears in Morrison's use of the old historical methodological such as the myth of the Africans flying to their continent to display the mingling of fantasy and history in the novel, and by involving this myth with the history of slavery in America and how some of them escapes from their destiny by going back to Africa as it is taken from the chronological description of history. Added to that, Toni Morrison re-writes the history of the past by using an ordinary man as a protagonist who is according to historiographicmetafiction a proper type of retelling the past. Milkman's quest of searching for the gold of his family leads him to discover the history of his ancestors and the lost names of the black people whose names are buried with the past through the songs and the games of the children in his ancestor's town as a way of hitting the point in the present and recalling the history of the past. In fact, Morrison's major goal is to evoke the history of her ancestors as an Afro-American individual by which she was able to use "*Song of Solomon*" and its protagonist, Milkman, in a way of searching for the lost identity among the bones of the past so as to show the correlation between fact and fiction.

3-Conclusion

The recent study exemplifies an analysis of a postmodern novel according to Hutcheon's model, historiographic metafiction, to illustrate the relation between facts and fiction by following Morrison's historical representation in her novel, *Song of Solomon*. "Historiographic metafiction" is the mixture of history and fiction that enables the writers to re-write history and generate substitute history as the utmost genre captured by the Afro-American writers. This paper comes up with the following findings:

1- *Historiographic Metafiction* is an appropriate narrative technique for Toni Morrison's *Song of Solomon* by which this approach catches the mangling of history and the fantasy in this novel throughout the presenting of the myth of flying back to Africa as a means of escaping from slavery in the American continent as well as by re-writing the suppressed past of the Afro-Americans.

2- *Song of Solomon* demonstrates the potentials of historical pastiche and self-reflexivity in the quest of searching for identity by using the quest of Milkman through a series of historical facts.

3- There is a relationship between history and fiction. Morrison's *Song of Solomon* is a sample of employing historiographic metafiction as a method of showing this relationship via presenting the lost identity of the Afro-Americans, which is depicted as a historical fact through the black fiction.

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